

Friction Tests on Oils for use on Motor-car Engines.

BY

E. R. WATSON, M.A., D.Sc.,

Principal,

AND

H. M. MULANY, M.Sc.,

Research Assistant, Technological Institute,

U. P., Calcutta.

These tests were undertaken to see whether a cheaper oil could not be used as a substitute for the expensive motor-car engine oils now on the market. It was first of all necessary to ascertain what laboratory tests a satisfactory oil must answer. It was decided to test a variety of oils, including some well-known motor-car oils and some cheaper oils such as cylinder oils, engine oils, spindle oils and castor oil, on a friction-testing machine at temperatures up to 100° or 120°C under moderate pressures (up to 60 lbs. per sq. in.) as it was thought these were about the conditions under which an oil had to operate in lubricating the walls of motor-car engine cylinders. It was expected that some oils would not be able to prevent solid friction at these high temperatures and such oils would have to be discarded as unsuitable for the purpose under consideration. Of those oils which could prevent solid friction the best would be those which had the lowest friction co-efficient both at this high temperature and also at lower temperatures. A small Thurston's friction-testing machine was used and

the following families of curves may be taken as typical of the results obtained :—

1. Mobiloil B (Vacuum Oil Co.).
2. Motor Oil B (Burmah Oil Co.).
3. Castor oil.
4. Standard Gas Engine Oil (Standard Oil Co.).
5. Cylinder Oil No. 660 (Burmah Oil Co.).
6. Red Engine Oil No. 2 (Standard Oil Co.).
7. Spindle Oil No. 40 (Burmah Oil Co.).

These curves were all obtained at a speed of 1,000 to 2,000 revolutions per minute and generally between 1,700 and 2,000. Friction was found to be practically independent of speed under the conditions of these experiments.

These tests were all carried to as high a temperature as possible and the ends of the curves on the high temperature side indicate the maximum temperatures at which the oils were able to prevent solid friction. (There are a few exceptions where solid friction did not set in even at the highest temperatures attained. In these cases a + sign is placed at the end of the curve.) When solid friction set in the co-efficient of friction began to rise very rapidly and Diagram 8 (Castrol T at 30 lbs. pressure) may be taken as typical of the curves obtained. In the above families (Diagrams 1—7) all the curves have been cut short just where the friction began to rise. In the small testing machine which we used there is no means of replacing the oil which works out of the bearing so the machine was stopped as soon as solid friction set in, a fresh quantity of oil applied to the bearing and running resumed as quickly as possible. In all cases the normal curves (friction decreasing with rise of temperature) were carried as far as possible by renewing the oil. The information obtained as regards limiting temperatures, *i.e.*, the maximum temperatures at which the oils could

prevent solid friction, is summarised in Diagram 9 which gives the limiting temperatures under different pressures for the various oils examined. (A curious feature is that many oils would not stand such a high temperature at intermediate pressures as they would at higher pressures.) Judging from the maximum temperatures at which an oil can be used without solid friction setting in, the order of merit for the oils examined is:—

Castor Oil	will stand up to 90°C
B. O. C. cylinder oil No. 660	” ” ” ”
Castrol T	” ” ” ”
Castrol R (if anomalous behaviour at 50 lbs. can be overlooked)	” ” ” ”
Mobiloil B	” ” ” 70°C
Standard gas engine oil	” ” ” 60°C
Castrol F	” ” ” 50°C
B. O. C. Motor Oil B	” ” ” 50°C
Red Engine Oil	” ” ” 40°C
Spindle Oil B. O. C. no. 40	” ” ” 30°C

But we must also take into account friction at ordinary temperature because an oil with a high friction at ordinary temperatures would make an engine very difficult to start. If we assume that any oil showing a friction higher than 5 lbs. per sq. inch at 30°C under any pressure up to 60 lbs. per sq. inch is unsatisfactory, this rules out Castor Oil, B. O. C. Cylinder Oil No. 660, and Castrol R and leaves the order of merit

- Castrol T.
- Mobiloil B.
- Standard Gas Engine Oil.
- Castrol F.
- B. O. C. Motor Oil B.
- Red Engine Oil.
- Spindle Oil.

If the oil will perform the required function at all the

less friction it gives the better. This consideration gives a slight preference to Castrol T.

As a conclusion from these considerations it will be seen that the oils on the market as motor-car engine oils answer the tests better than the other oils examined, such as castor oil, cylinder, engine and spindle oils. The only other oil examined which answered the tests was Standard Gas Engine Oil.

But these experiments showed us that the temperature at which solid friction occurs depends a great deal on the supply of oil. With a more efficient system for continuously supplying oil to the moving parts the maximum temperature attainable without solid friction can be increased. We may assume that if used with a better arrangement for oil supply the order of merit would remain the same; but this is an assumption which may or may not be justified. Trying to test this point we had a couple of oil tubes bored through the upper brass of the small Thurston's machine and had these fitted with oil cups. This was an imperfect arrangement and the thinner oils flowed through the bearing so quickly that it was difficult to keep the cups filled and a large quantity of oil was used for each test. We find from Archbutt and Dealey's book on lubricants that friction-testing machines with more efficient oil supply have been designed and would be more suitable for these tests. However, with the apparatus at our disposal we arrived at the interesting conclusion that even the lightest oil in our selection, *viz.*, Spindle Oil B. O. C. No. 40, could be used up to 100°C without solid friction setting in (diagram 10). Moreover on our modified machine Spindle Oil gave a more satisfactory test than Castrol T; and of course if there was no danger of solid friction the lighter oil would be preferable to the heavier as its co-efficient of liquid friction is less. All appears to depend, then, on the

DIAGRAM 2.—MOTOR OIL B.

Friction in lbs. per sq. inch of bearing surface = Arbitrary Scale reading $\times 0.127$

- at 10 lbs. pressure per sq. inch.
- " 20 " " " "
- " 30 " " " "
- . - . " 40 " " " "
- . . - " 50 " " " "
- . — . " 60 " " " "

DIAGRAM 3.—CASTOR OIL.

Friction in lbs. per sq. inch of bearing surface = Arbitrary Scale reading $\times 0.127$

- at 10 lbs. pressure per sq. inch.
- " 20 " " " " "
- — — " 30 " " " " "
- · - · " 40 " " " " "
- · · - " 50 " " " " "
- · — · " 60 " " " " "

DIAGRAM 4.—STANDARD GAS ENGINE OIL.

Friction in lbs. per sq. inch of bearing surface = Arbitrary Scale reading $\times 0.127$

—————	at 10 lbs. pressure per sq. inch.
.....	" 20 " " " " "
— — — —	" 30 " " " " "
— . — . — .	" 40 " " " " "
— . . . — .	" 50 " " " " "
— — — —	" 60 " " " " "

DIAGRAM 5.—CYLINDER OIL No. 660

Friction in lbs. per sq. inch of bearing surface = Arbitrary Scale reading $\times 0.127$

—————	at 10 lbs. pressure per sq inch.
.....	" 20 " " " "
— — — —	" 30 " " " "
- . - . - .	" 40 " " " "
— · — · — ·	" 50 " " " "
- - - - -	" 60 " " " "

DIAGRAM 6.—RED ENGINE OIL NO. 2.

Friction in lbs per sq. inch of bearing surface = Arbitrary Scale reading $\times 0.127$

—————	at 10 lbs	pressure per sq. inch.
.....	" 20 "	" " " "
— · — · —	" 30 "	" " " "
— · — · —	" 40 "	" " " "
— · — · —	" 50 "	" " " "
— · — · —	" 60 "	" " " "

DIAGRAM 7.—SPINDLE OIL No. 40.

Friction in lbs. per sq. inch of bearing surface = Arbitrary Scale reading $\times 0.127$

- at 10 lbs. pressure per sq. inch.
- " 20 " " " " "
- · — · — " 30 " " " " "
- · · — · " 40 " " " " "
- · · · — " 50 " " " " "
- · · · · " 60 " " " " "

DIAGRAM 8.—CASTROL T.

(At 30 lbs. pressure per sq. inch.)

Friction in lbs. per sq. inch of bearing surface = Arbitrary Scale reading $\times 0.127$

— with 1st supply of oil.
 " 2nd " " "

DIAGRAM 9.—LIMITING TEMPERATURE—PRESSURE CURVES.

- | | | | |
|-----------|----------------------|---------|------------------------------------|
| — | stands for Castrol T | — o o | stands for Standard Gas Engine Oil |
| | " " Castrol R | — — — | " " Cylinder Oil No. 680 |
| o o o o o | " " Mobil Oil B | — . . — | " " Rod Engine Oil No. 2 |
| — — — | " " Motor Oil B | — o — | " " Spindle Oil No. 40 |
| — . . . | " " Castor Oil | — x — | " " Castrol F |

DIAGRAM 10.—SPINDLE OIL, No. 40.

(Tested on modified friction-testing machine.)

Friction in lbs. per sq. inch of bearing surface = Arbitrary Scale reading $\times 0.127$

—————	at 10 lbs. pressure per sq. inch.
.....	" 20 " " " "
— — — —	" 30 " " " "
- . - . - .	" 40 " " " "
- . . - .	" 50 " " " "
— — — —	" 60 " " " "

efficiency of the mechanical arrangements for the supply of oil to the moving parts of the motor-car engine. With an inefficient system the motor-car engine oils on the market are the best to use, but with a more perfect system it should be possible to use a lighter oil and get a much better mileage from the fuel owing to decreased friction.

The Spindle Oil was tried in a Dodge car but after a few miles the white metal was burnt out from one of the big-end bearings. In this car there is a combination pump and splash feed oiling system and it is not known whether the oil failed because it was too thin for the pump to circulate it properly or whether the pressure on the big end bearing was too great for such a thin oil. There was no obvious trouble as regards the lubrication of the cylinder walls and it may be that we have exaggerated the importance of this part of motor-car engine lubrication. Obviously the only safe way to arrive at a conclusion as to the relative merits of different motor-car engine lubricants is to test them thoroughly in a motor-car engine, or, preferably in a number of engines with different lubricating systems. Nevertheless it was thought that our laboratory experiments were sufficiently interesting to be put on record.

GOVERNMENT TECHNOLOGICAL INSTITUTE,
U. P., CAWNPORE, INDIA.

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